

ANALYSIS OF A WORK OF ART IN ITS HISTORICAL AND CULTURAL CONTEXT

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Abstract. *The article notes the existing productive methods of analyzing a literary text and discusses new approaches that allow useful and effective research of literary works, revealing their ideological, artistic, thematic, figurative and stylistic basis.*

Keywords: *professional competence, competence, knowledge, ability, skills, motivational-value component.*

The analysis of work that art continues to be one of the urgent problems of modern literary criticism. The article notes that the existing productive methods of analyzing a literary text and discusses new approaches that allow useful and effective research of literary works, revealing their ideological, artistic, thematic, figurative and stylistic basis. Particular attention is paid to the study of the work as a "communicatively conditioned coherent whole", the need for a systematic approach to the consideration of the text and the importance of conducting a comprehensive analysis of the art work. Understanding a work of art in its broad historical and cultural context allows for a multi-level detailed analysis of the work as a complex system, revealing its various levels.

As you know, literature is an important means of forming the spiritual world of a person, his morality and artistic taste. Since works of fiction "have more energy-informational potential than texts of other styles", they represent an inexhaustible source of ideas and knowledge and largely determine the development of human intelligence. Texts are also a special way of transmitting the spiritual heritage of the past from generation to generation, since "by creating and perceiving works of art, a person transmits, receives and stores special artistic information that is inseparable from the structural features of artistic texts ...". The values of culture, history and words are preserved through careful attitude, love and reverence for works of fiction, since a person "is brought up not only by the results of the ancestral thoughts extracted from communication with people ..., but also by the works of previous centuries". This transfer of information is important both for students studying literature and readers, critics and especially writers, since "the richer the past literature and the more extensive use of it, the more diverse new works can be with equality of other things".

At the present stage of cultural development, the problem of perception and understanding of the text becomes particularly acute. Of great importance is the identification of the ideological, thematic, figurative and aesthetic specifics of the work of art, the consideration of its individual originality and the definition of the author's message to a wide readership. Close attention to works of art is determined, on the one hand, by the need to comprehend the classical heritage of the past and preserve its enduring significance, and on the other hand, by the importance of understanding the new literary situation and penetrating into the essence of works created by modern authors. Such texts, as a rule, are difficult to perceive, understand and study. The analysis of a work of art is especially significant in our time, when interest in the book is decreasing, and the importance of facts obtained from the mass media, especially from the Internet, is increasing. Reading becomes

superficial not only for the mass reader, but also for students whose knowledge is diffuse, fragmented and mosaic, often not forming one overall picture.

Knowledge of the literary heritage allows you to navigate "in a variety of cultural systems and guess the direction of further development of the literary process", as well as to evaluate the creative searches of modern authors based on rethinking literary masterpieces of the past, creating new narratives that carry a variety of ideas and a wealth of meanings.

Works of art considered as complex multilevel organized systems, when properly read, provide the reader with knowledge about culture in various epochs, about the peculiarities of human life, his inner world, spiritual quest and moral ideals, since "any work of art, any artistic trend is both a phenomenon of the reality that gave rise to them, and part of the universal continuum, the result of the accumulated experience of mankind". The texts reflect the complexity of relations in a modern globalized society and capture a wide variety of knowledge about the world and life in various genre forms. Meaningful insight into the essence of the works will allow students to independently identify the features of artistic thinking encoded in the text, and will contribute to the formation of thoughtful readers who will be able to work with the art of words and discover new depths of meaning and aesthetic value of the literary heritage of the past.

The main part. As is known, "literary analysis is the study of parts and elements of a work, as well as the connections between them". A broad understanding of the term "text analysis" includes not only the division of the fabric of an artistic narrative into parts and components, its components and their detailed study, but also work at a high level of generalization of information.

Currently, there are a large number of methods and approaches to the analysis of literary phenomena and works of art. We will allow you to identify only the main approaches, concepts and methodological systems proposed by some authors. It should be noted that the dialectical method does not lose its significance in the modern world, since it assumes "consideration of any phenomena of reality in development and mutual connection" and is actively used in the analysis of a work of art. A coherent system of methods for the study of a work of art is presented by Russian professor N.S. Bolotnova [1, p 26]. According to her scheme, the methods of philological analysis of the text include general scientific methods (observation, quantitative analysis, modeling, experiment, comparative), general philological methods (transformational method, distributive analysis, contextual analysis, component analysis, compositional analysis, structural method, semiotic method, conceptual analysis); private methods (intertextual analysis, method close to experiment, word-image method, semiotic-stylistic method, comparative-stylistic method).

Theorists V.G. Zinchenko, V.G. Zusman and Z.I. Kirnose [2, p 44] in their work "Literature and methods of its study: a system-synergetic approach" note the following methods as the most productive: biographical method, cultural-historical method and hermeneutics (they study the work as a complex hierarchical system); formal and structural method; sociological method (focused on the author–reality, reader–reality relationship); receptive aesthetics, comparative historical method and comparative studies. These researchers also distinguish systematic and system-synergetic approaches and note that "each of the literary methods, if it does not claim to be universal, can open up some side of the study of fiction".

V.A. Lukov considers "a combination of a historical and theoretical approach that arose within the framework of literary studies, but allows to explore other phenomena of artistic culture, and a general humanitarian thesaurus approach" [3, p. 8], emphasizing their fruitful coexistence.

Some researchers talk about the problem of the synthesis of literary approaches in the framework of the study of the triad "author – text – reader", emphasizing the importance of receptive aesthetics, narratology and historical-functional approach. They claim that "the study of the relations between the components of the triad indicates an increasing role of the communicative function of the work of art, which determines a fundamentally different (compared with traditional approaches) orientation of the literary text".

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